

THREE DIMENSIONAL DAMAGE PREDICTION OF LAMINATES UNDER LOW VELOCITY IMPACT

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ABSTRACT

The poor tolerance of composite laminates to accidental low velocity impacts is a limitation to their use in industry. Ignoring the consequences of impact loading and the difficulty in measuring the evolution of damage versus time impose actually a high safety factor for the design of structures, about ten in the marine industry, compared to a factor of two for static loading. For this reason, our objective is to develop numerical tools which are able to predict the behaviour of real structures.

BENEFIT TO A STUDY IN A DYNAMIC CONTEXT

A low velocity impact is characterized by a velocity lower than 5 m/s, a mass lower than 5 kg, for a maximum incident energy of 60 J. The dynamic characterization of laminates under this kind of loading is difficult to set-up. It is often replaced by static indentation tests at the same energy [1]. A comparison between dynamic tests, carried out from a drop-weight set-up, and static indentation tests has been done on ten plies symmetrical 0/90 glass-epoxy laminates [2]. A drop-weight set-up, using the Split Hopkinson Pressure Bars technique, allows a precise measurement of the resultant force and of the normal displacement of the extremity of the projectile versus time, (Fig. 1) [3]. The projectile is a long rod (600 mm, \varnothing 25 mm) with a hemispherical end. The tested plates are glass-epoxy ten-ply laminates [0n/90m/0n] (\varnothing = 200 mm, thickness = 1.9 mm) clamped over a ring 20 mm wide on their periphery. The static indentation test is carried out using the same hemispherical end of the indenter and the same clamping system. The structural heterogeneity of the composite leads to a multi-scale damage : matrix cracking and delamination. But, if we compare the damage under static loading and under impact, for the same energy applied, we observe differences from 50 to 100 % in the extent of the damage area and different damage events (fibres rupture under static loading), (Fig. 2). The greater the energy, the larger the difference. During impact, the local effect of the applied load is not seen at the same time by all the points of the structure. Moreover, the duration of the loading is different. Even with low velocity impacts, the dynamic aspect of the shock must not be neglected. It is unwise to generalize the substitution of dynamic tests by static indentation experiments.

Figure 1 : comparison between damage under dynamic (left) and static (right) loading glass-epoxy [02/906/02] - applied energy : 27 J - loaded face - scale 1:1

Figure 2 : experimental drop-weight set-up

THREE-DIMENSIONAL REPRESENTATION OF THE COMPOSITE STRUCTURE

The response of the composite plates under low velocity impact loading is modelled with the dynamic explicit finite element code PLEXUS. The fundamental system of equations to solve in a dynamic finite element code is, after space and time discretizations, Eqn (1) :

$$\begin{cases} \{u^n\}, \{\dot{u}^n\}, \{\ddot{u}^n\} \text{ known} \\ [M] \{\ddot{u}^{n+1}\} = \{F_{ext}^{n+1}\} - \{F_{int}^{n+1}\} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $\{u^n\}$, $\{\dot{u}^n\}$, $\{\ddot{u}^n\}$ are nodal displacements, velocities and accelerations at time step n , $[M]$ is the lumped mass matrix, $\{F_{ext}\}$ is the vector of the external forces applied on the nodes of the mesh and $\{F_{int}\}$ is the vector of internal forces. No stiffness matrix needs to be assembled. The numerical integration scheme of Newmark is used in its explicit formulation :

$$\begin{cases} u^{n+1} = u^n + \Delta t \dot{u}^n + \frac{\Delta t^2}{2} \ddot{u}^n \\ \ddot{u}^{n+1} = \ddot{u}^n + \frac{\Delta t}{2} (\ddot{u}^n + \ddot{u}^{n+1}) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

A contact model has been developed from the Lagrange multiplier technique to represent the impact loading [4]. The coupling conditions between matrix cracking (volumetric damage) and delamination (surface damage) lead to a three dimensional representation of the laminate.

CHOICE OF THE ELEMENTS

For the previously defined range of energy, a low velocity transverse impact on a laminate induces a primarily bending behaviour of the structure. Elements with some degrees of freedom in rotation, i.e. a semi-C1 continuity between elements, must be chosen to ensure a better representation of the real displacements. Unfortunately, these elements are not yet programmed

in σ PLEXUS. We have used only hexahedric elements with a C0 continuity and three degrees of freedom in translation, which can induce a numerical global rigidity of the structure. Two kinds of C0 hexahedric elements are used to represent the laminates. The full "hyphen" integration elements are in the impact zone to control the time step, the single integration one elsewhere [5]. To ensure a representative calculation of the stresses in the full-integration elements used in the mesh, we propose to approach them as follows during one time step : first the stresses at the centre of the element for the damage process are calculated. They will not numerically be stored, but will be used for the damage criterion, its initiation and its propagation; a second classical calculation of the stresses at the integration points is then carried out using the previous modifications due to the damage modelling, for the determination of the nodal internal forces with the updated mechanical characteristics of the material.

INDIVIDUAL MODELLING OF EACH PLY

The experimental study shows volumetric damage which differs according to their location in the thickness of the plate. Each ply S_k is considered as an independent structure with n hexahedric brick elements V_k . The time step, which controls the transfer speed of the actions within the mesh, is defined for long fibres composite materials as (1 is the direction of the fibres of the ply, 2 and 3 are the transverse directions) :

$$\Delta t_s = \frac{l_{\min}}{c_1} \quad \text{if } E_1 > E_2 = E_3 \quad (3)$$

In terms of wave propagation, the transfer speed has no physical meaning if $l_{\min} \neq l_1$. Whatever the stacking sequence, a common direction to all the elements is the thickness of the plies (3rd direction). The following ratio is chosen to transfer the actions with a speed equal, at least, to the material wave velocity in one direction of the mesh :

$$\Delta t_s = \frac{l_3}{c_3} \quad \text{gives} \quad \underset{i=1,3}{\text{Min}} \frac{l_i}{c_i} \quad (4)$$

The new time step respects the stability condition of the integration scheme and is greater than the previous one. This reduces the duration of the calculation by a factor of 2 if $E_1 = 4 E_3$ for example. The elements at the centre of the plate, near the loading area, have the smallest size to limit dispersion during the numerical transfer of the actions [5].

ASSEMBLY OF THE LAMINATE

The plies are tied together by assembly conditions on the double nodes of the mesh. The pre-existing node-on-node contact allows the development of the Lagrange multiplier technique on the mesoscale [5]. For each double node (N_k, N_{k+1}) of the interface, a link force is calculated to keep the equality of the displacements, Eqn 5. This leads to a perfect transmission of the loading in each direction of space. This modelling is, a priori, well adapted to a dynamic explicit code.

$$F_{\text{link}} = \pm \frac{m_{N_k} (F_{\text{ext}}^{N_{k+1}} - F_{\text{int}}^{N_{k+1}}) - m_{N_{k+1}} (F_{\text{ext}}^{N_k} - F_{\text{int}}^{N_k})}{m_{N_k} + m_{N_{k+1}}} \quad (5)$$

with $m_{N_k}, m_{N_{k+1}}$, the masses on nodes N_k et N_{k+1}
 $F_{\text{ext}}^{N_k}, F_{\text{ext}}^{N_{k+1}}$, the external forces on nodes N_k et N_{k+1}
 $F_{\text{int}}^{N_k}, F_{\text{int}}^{N_{k+1}}$, the internal forces on nodes N_k et N_{k+1} .

A three dimensional modelling by means of hexahedric elements is done to allow a fine representation of the physical phenomena [6], but this representation needs long calculations with sequential computing. Nevertheless, the concept of independent ply and the assembly technique of the laminate by means of the Lagrange multiplier method lends itself to parallel processing.

DAMAGE MODELLING

MATRIX CRACKING

The effects of cracks are calculated on average by the evolution of the mechanical characteristics in the direction normal to the fibres, within each element [5]. The matrix cracking model is adapted from the results of [7]. The damage parameter η is the number of cracks of the element. The initiation and propagation criterion concerns the evolution of the material transverse component of the stresses tensor, σ_{22} , and the sign of the strains in the direction 2 and 3, to ensure a physical cracking opening due to an extension of the material. When the criterion is reached, the dilution parameter β , linked to the number of cracks in the element, can be calculated. If we suppose that the variation of stress is low during one time step, which is verified numerically, we can assume the appearance of only one crack in the element during the time step :

$$\Delta\sigma^{n+1} \ll \sigma^n \Rightarrow \eta_e = 1 \Rightarrow \beta = \frac{2 a}{l_{tf}} \tag{6}$$

with l_{tf} the length of the elements in the transverse fibre direction calculated on the deformed structure, and η_e the number of cracks in V_k .

If M is the initial compliance tensor of the material with h cracks, the new compliance tensor \tilde{M} of the equivalent material without crack is given, as a function of β , by :

$$\tilde{M} = M + \frac{\Pi}{4} \beta \Lambda \tag{7}$$

with Λ the tensor of interaction between matrix and cracks

As the stress increment is low between two time step, we assume the appearance of one crack only in the non damaged material of the configuration p . The number of cracks in the initial material (at $t=0$) increases virtually by one :

$$\eta_e^{p+1} = \eta_e^p + 1 \tag{8}$$

To take into account a saturated state of cracks in the element V_k , we postulate that the element V_k is saturated with cracks if the number of cracks in the initial material is above a critical value calculated as a function of the thickness and the length of the element in the deformed structure. The smaller the size of the element, the greater the effect of the presence of one crack, and the lower the saturated state. The experimental observations show that the critical number of cracks depends on the position of the ply in the thickness of the laminate. Several β_e^{limit} values must be determined for each ply from :

$$\eta_e < \eta_e^{crit} = \frac{l_e}{2 a} \beta_e^{limit} / ply \tag{9}$$

DELAMINATION

The experimental observations show that matrix cracking is a forrunner of delamination. The delamination appears if both plies at the interface are cracked, and if the lower ply is saturated with cracks [2]. This phenomenon is expressed by a necessary condition of localization concerning the cracking state previously defined. The two components, N_k (upper ply as regards the interface) and N_{k+1} (lower ply) of a double node at the interface, have the same displacements. Each node belongs to a different ply and is common to several elements. To localize the delamination at the interface, at least one element adjacent to node N_k must be cracked, and all the elements adjacent to node N_{k+1} must be saturated with cracks. Experimentally, the localization of the delamination is followed by a propagation in the direction

of the fibres of the lower ply. The propagation is due to a preponderant influence of mode II cracking on the relative displacements of the interface. The node-on-node assembly of the laminate, by means of the link force, leads us to propose an initiation criterion on the interfacial forces. The criterion is based on the component, at node N_k or N_{k+1} , of the interfacial forces in the direction of the fibres of the lower ply. If the localization criterion is reached, and if the value of the link force exceeds a critical value, a local loss of contact occurs at the interface. The link forces are cancelled in the three directions of the space. This could be summarize by Eqn (10) :

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \eta_i > 0 \\ \eta_j = \eta_c^{crit} \\ F_{\alpha}^{node N_k} > F_{\alpha}^{critical} \end{array} \right. \Rightarrow \{A\} = \{0\} \Rightarrow \{F_{link}\} = \{0\} \quad (10)$$

with i an adjacent element of node N_k
and j all the adjacent elements of node N_{k+1} .

Moreover, the separation of the interfacial double nodes needs a control of their displacements after delamination so that they do not penetrate the opposite face. The classical tests for the search of contact in three dimensions are applied. In case of penetration, a back-force is calculated from the conservation of the momentum between the slave and the defending node without any contact conservation [5].

APPLICATION

The impact-force, the matrix-cracking and the delamination modelling are here applied to the impact of a circular laminated plate (diameter 200 mm). The numerical test corresponds to the experimental drop-weight set-up previously described in the first paragraph. The plate is a [03/904/03] glass epoxy laminate clamped on its periphery over a ring of 20 mm. The effect of the manufacturing conditions of the composite plate, i.e. curing in an oven without pressure, are taken into account in the modelling of the damage (delamination). Each group of plies has the following elastic properties :

$E_1 = 30.5 \text{ GPa}$	$E_2 = 5.1 \text{ GPa}$	$E_3 = 5.1 \text{ GPa}$
$\nu_{12} = 0.33$	$\nu_{13} = 0.33$	$\nu_{23} = 0.6$
$G_{12} = 1.9 \text{ GPa}$	$G_{13} = 1.9 \text{ GPa}$	$G_{23} = 1.6 \text{ GPa}$

NUMERICAL REPRESENTATION OF THE DROP-WEIGHT SET-UP

The thickness of the laminate is 1,9 mm for 10 plies. We use only one hexahedric element in the thickness per group of plies :

- one element of 3 x 0,19 mm to represent the first three plies at 0°
- one element of 4 x 0,19 mm to represent the four medium plies at 90°
- one element of 3 x 0,19 mm to represent the last three plies at 0°

The total number of hexahedric elements used for meshing the plate is 924 for three groups of plies (12 elements with 8 integration points under impact, 912 one integration point elements). For reasons of calculation time, it is not practical to use a cubic shape for the elements of the mesh all over the plate.

The boundary conditions are very strong and are represented as the suppression of the displacements at the periphery of the plate.

The projectile is represented by a massive point. Its mass and velocity are the same as the real projectile. It will impact the centre of the plate (Fig 3). In term of representation of the overall response of the composite structure under low velocity impact, this approximation is allowed.

Figure 3 : view of deformed mesh (one hexahedric element per layer)
Scale 0.4

HYBRID APPROACH FOR THE DETERMINATION OF THE VALUES OF THE CRITERIA

To determine the values of the matrix cracking and delamination criteria, an hybrid approach mixing experimental and numerical aspects is used [8]. Some experimental testings at increasing energies give the instant of the first damage by comparison with the maximum force recorded. A first calculation, without any damage modelling, gives at the instant of appearance of the first damage, the values of the quantities of the criterion. Then, a second calculation with the damage modelling is done to validate the criterion by comparison with experimental results. The following values of the criterion have been found :

$$\text{- matrix cracking criterion : } \delta = 100 \Rightarrow \sigma_{22}^{\max} = \frac{E_2}{100} = 51 \text{ MPa}$$

$$\text{- delamination criterion : } \beta_{\text{limit}/0^\circ} = 0.5 \text{ and } \beta_{\text{limit}/90^\circ} = 2$$

$$F_{\alpha}^{\text{crit}} = 250 \text{ N}$$

RESULTS

For an impact of 27 J (mass of 2.3 kg, velocity of 5 m/s), three series of results are presented and compared with experimental measurements. First, the macroscopical response of the plate by means of the displacements of the centre of the plate and the impact force versus time is shown (Fig. 4) and (Fig. 5). The distribution of the matrix cracking in the three groups of plies and the delamination area at the interfaces are presented (Fig 6) with the comparison of experimental observations. Good agreement is obtained between numerical and real damage.

Figure 4 : vertical displacements of the impact point vs. time (at the centre of the plate)

Figure 5 : resultant impact forces vs time

Figure 6 : matrix cracking within each ply (top) - delamination at each interface (bottom) for an impact of 27 J on a glass-epoxy [03/904/03] laminate

CONCLUSION

This paper presents some tools to simulate the low velocity impact damage of laminated composite structures. The proposed modelling is designed to be well adapted to the numerical structure of a dynamic explicit code. It needs some experimental data in the frame of the hybrid approach, i.e. synergy between experimental, theoretical and numerical aspects [8]. First, a model of contact-impact is presented from the Lagrange multiplier technique. This model allows a three-dimensional representation of the laminate. Then, the matrix cracking is represented by an averaging technique developed on the scale of a finite element. The delamination is defined as a 3D debonding of the interfacial nodes, coupled with the matrix-cracking damage. These models are applied to the impact of 27 J of a ten plies [0/90]_s glass-epoxy plate. In this case, only four parameters must be identified by the hybrid approach. The results show good agreement between the experimental and numerical damage observations.

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